

Empowerment and Job Commitment among Nursing Educators

Abeer Mohamed Abd-Elkader, Lecturer

Nursing Education, Faculty of Nursing, El-Minia University

Naglaa Saad Abdel-Atti, Lecturer

Community Health Nursing, Faculty of Nursing, Assiut University

Abstract

*One important factor in continuity of any organization is human resources that are considered by organizations' managers. Employee engagement and commitment are major success factors for the organizations. Empowerment heightens employees' sense of personal control and motivates them to engage in work, which in turn results in positive managerial and organizational outcomes. **Objective:** To identify the relationship between empowerment and job commitment among nursing educators. **Setting:** The study was carried out at faculty of nursing in El-Minia University. **Subjects:** The study subjects included a total number of 80 nursing educators. **Tool:** Empowerment and Job Commitment Questionnaire was used to collect the necessary data. **Results:** A statistically significant positive weak correlation between empowerment and job commitment of the studied educators was revealed. Where, the studied educators had moderate level of empowerment and high level of job commitment. **Conclusion:** It can be concluded that self-determination was the highest ranked psychological empowerment dimension and workplace culture was the highest ranked structural empowerment dimension. **Recommendations:** It was recommended to develop trust, fairness, and better communication to nursing educators through good team working, respect for the roles and contributions of others.*

Keywords: Structural empowerment, Psychological empowerment, Job commitment, Nursing educators.

Introduction

One important factor in continuity of organization is human resources that are considered by organizations' managers and responsible. Employee engagement and commitment are major success factors in organizations⁽¹⁾. Empowerment heightens employees' sense of personal control and motivates them to engage in work, which in turn results in positive managerial and organizational outcomes⁽²⁾.

In addition, empowerment is a continuous interactive process because each individual and team that earns the power and authority applies it^(3,4). Ahmad et al. (2014) they suggests four important factors for employees' empowerment; first involving employees in decision making,

second involving employees in programming process, third appreciating employees, fourth providing employees with continuous training and support⁽⁵⁾. Moreover, there are two dimensions of empowerment **a) Structural empowerment:** the perception of the presence or *absence of conditions that were empowering in the workplace*) and **b) Psychological empowerment:** *the employees' psychological interpretation or reaction to these conditions*)⁽⁶⁾.

Structural empowerment components includes; **1) Sociopolitical support**, to measure the perception of the vertical and lateral support in the workplace. Its statements as (a) I have the support, I need from my superior to do my job well, (b) I have the support, I need from my peers to do my job well, (c) (I have the

support, I need from subordinates to do my job well. **2) Access to Information**, to measure the perception of information relates to the data, technical knowledge, and expertise required to perform one's job and an understanding of organization vision and goals. Its statements as (a) I have access to the strategic information, I need to do my job well, (b) I understand top management's. **3) Access to Resources**, to measure the perceptions of availability and privilege of acquiring resources to do the job. Its statements as (a) I have access to the resources, I need to do my job well, (b) I can obtain the resources to support new ideas and improvement in my department, (c) When I need additional resources to do my job, I can usually get them. **4) Agency/Unit Culture**, to measure perception of the working climate with respect to participation, flexibility, recognition of employee ideas, problem-solving, and cohesion. Its statements as (a) Participation and open discussion, (b) Flexibility and decentralization, (c) Assessment of employee concerns and ideas, (d) Creative problem-solving processes, (e) Human relations, teamwork, cohesion^(7,8).

The four components of **psychological empowerment** are as follows: (1) *Meaning* involves a fit between the needs of one's work role and one's beliefs, values and behaviors. (2) *Competence* refers to self-efficacy specific to one's work, or a belief in one's capability to perform work activities with skill. (3) *Self-determination* is a sense of choice in initiating and regulating one's actions. It reflects a sense of autonomy or choice over the initiation and continuation of work behavior and processes (e.g., making decisions about work methods, pace, and effort). (4) *Impact* is the degree to which one can influence strategic, administrative, or operating outcomes at work⁽⁹⁾.

Ahmad et al. (2014) they showed a strong correlation between teachers' perception of their empowerment and their

commitment to their organization, teaching, and their display of organization citizenship behavior⁽⁵⁾. Job commitment is an employee's "identification" and "involvement" with the organization they work in. In essence, job commitment exists when a person accepts and believes in the organization's mission and vision, and is willing to engage and participate in the organization. These individuals want to play an active role in the organization—they want to have impact, they want to feel they have some weight in the organization, and as such are willing to contribute more^(10,11). Job Commitment, and likewise, Occupational or Professional Commitment, is defined as a psychological link between the employee and their employing organization (or their profession) that may determine the stability of and adherence to their employment^(12,13).

El-Din and Abd-El-Rahman (2013) defined 3 components to job commitment: (1) *Affective* commitment relates to how much employees want to stay at their organization⁽¹⁴⁾. If an employee is affectively committed to their organization, it means that they want to stay at their organization. They typically identify with the organizational goals, feel that they fit into the organization and are satisfied with their work. Employees who are affectively committed feel valued, act as ambassadors for their organization and are generally great assets for organizations⁽¹⁴⁾. (2) *Continuance* commitment relates to how much employees feel the need to stay at their organization. In employees that are continuance committed, the underlying reason for their commitment lies in their need to stay with the organization. Possible reasons for needing to stay with organizations vary, but the main reasons relate to a lack of work alternatives, and remuneration, (3) *Normative* commitment is defined as an employee's sense of obligation to the organization. Normative commitment relates to how much employees feel they should stay at their organization. Employees that are

normatively committed generally feel that they should stay at their organizations. Normatively committed employees feel that leaving their organization would have disastrous consequences, and feel a sense of guilt about the possibility of leaving. Reasons for such guilt vary, but are often concerned with employees feeling that in leaving the organization they would create a void in knowledge/skills, which would subsequently increase the pressure on their colleagues. Such feelings can, and do, negatively influence the performance of employees working in organizations⁽¹⁴⁾.

The Three-Component of job Commitment was tested by Meyer et al. (2004) to explain why employees remained in an organization even if their experience was undesirable⁽¹⁵⁾. Those who perceive their experiences with the organization were meeting their expectations and satisfying their needs display affective commitment—want to stay. Those who have made investments (years, life alterations, equity in benefits) stay because they need to in order to avoid losses and were designated as continuance commitment—need to stay. Those who feel a strong loyalty and enjoy socialization experiences see the appropriateness of staying and were normatively committed to the organization—ought to stay^(16,17).

Nursing education today is one of the merits of the Ministry of Higher Education. Higher education in Egypt was established to enhance the nation's growth and the well-being of Egyptian people. There is a movement toward advanced nursing education in order to keep pace with today's health demand. The Nursing Faculties in Egypt have a mission. Typically, this mission covers teaching, research, and community service. Faculty members are the main structure of every university. Colleges and Universities need experienced teachers as one of the principles for education in order to raise scientific level of students. Lack of empowerment and job commitment among faculty members could

threaten their physical and mental health and life quality and could prevent achieving individual and social development. Faculty member's self-esteem, job satisfaction and organizational commitment in higher education have been given little attention by researchers in El-Minia faculty of nursing.

Furthermore, it is important to know nursing educator perceptions about their job's meaning and impact, and beliefs about their institutional commitment, promotion of nurse educator competence and self-determination, and information sharing. Such information may provide empirical data to aid higher education managers in creating a work environment conducive to recruiting and retaining nurse educator and may also contribute to better decisions by policymakers and others shaping nursing workforce development and nursing education systems in the future.

Aim of the Study

The aim of the present study to identify the relationship between empowerment and job commitment of nursing educators.

Research Questions:

- 1- Is there a relationship between nursing educators' sense of empowerment and their job commitment?
- 2- What are the factors affecting nursing educators empowerment?

Materials and Method

Materials

Design: A descriptive–correlational design was utilized.

Setting: The study was conducted at the Faculty of Nursing El-Minia University.

Subjects: The study subjects comprised all nursing educators working in the previously mentioned setting and who were available at the time of data collection (N = 80).

Tool:

Tool I: Empowerment and Job Commitment Questionnaire

Empowerment and job commitment questionnaire developed by Royer (2009) was used for data collection⁽¹⁸⁾. Empowerment and job commitment questionnaire was self-administered and respondents have 30 minutes to complete it. Respondents completing the questionnaire that composed of 48 items by using a 5-point likert scale from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*) to report their perceived level of empowerment, job commitment, and career change. Where one for strongly disagree, two for disagree, three for undecided, four for agree, and five for strongly agree. The questionnaire is scored by adding the items on each of the subscales:

Part I:

- a) *Demographic variables* such as age, gender, department, academic qualification.
- b) *Empowerment questionnaire* (27 items) subdivided into 8 subscales as 4 subscales related to psychological empowerment dimensions and 4 subscales related to structural empowerment dimensions. **Psychological** empowerment dimensions namely meaning (3 items), competence (3 items), self-determination (3 items), impact (3 items). **Structural** empowerment dimensions namely Sociopolitical Support (4 items), Access to Strategic Information (3 items), Access to Resources (3 items), and Workplace Culture (5 items). The total empowerment score ranges from 27 to 135. Studied subjects responses calculated as follows; low levels of empowerment are a score below 46, moderate levels range from 46 to 90, and high levels range from 91 to 135.

Part II:

Job Commitment questionnaire (18 items) subdivided into 3 subscales namely Affective Commitment (6 items), Continuance Commitment (6 items), and Normative Commitment (6 items). The total job Commitment level ranges from 18 to 90. Studied subjects responses calculated as follows; low levels of job Commitment are a score below 31, moderate levels range from 31 to 60, and high levels range from 61 to 90.

Method

- Permission to conduct the study was obtained from all responsible authorities of El-Minia Faculty of nursing (the dean and heads of departments) and after explanation the purpose of the study.
- Content validity of the tool was done by 4 experts in the related fields as follows; two professors from Nursing Education department Faculty of Nursing Alexandria University, two professors from Nursing Administration department Faculty of Nursing Cairo University. Reliability of the tool was calculated using Cronbach alpha $r = 0.97$
- A pilot study was carried out on a sample of 10% from Participants to check and ensure the clarity and applicability of the tools. Based on the results of the pilot study modifications, clarifications, omissions, and rearrangement of some questions were done. The pilot subjects were not included in the main study subjects.
- The questionnaire was administered individually to each participant in the study setting. It took 30 minutes to complete it.
- Data collection started from 1st October to 30th December 2013.

Ethical considerations:

Written consent of the participants was obtained after explaining the purpose of the study and ensuring that their participation was strictly voluntary. Confidentiality, privacy and anonymity of the participants and their responses was assured.

Statistical Analysis

The data from the participants entered and analyzed using statistical package for the social sciences software (SPSS) for windows (version 20). Data presented using descriptive statistic in the form of frequency and percentage. Also, Pearson correlation, Chi-square, and ANOVA test was calculated to evaluate the relationship between variables. P value of ≤ 0.05 used to assess the significance of the results.

Results

Table (1) shows the distribution of the nursing educators according to their general characteristics. More than fifty percent (51.25%) of the study subjects were within the $21 \leq 30$ age ranges. The majority (92.5%) were females. Moreover, regarding academic qualification of the studied nursing educators it was noticed that Baccalaureate degree represent 31.25%, Master degree represent 37.5%, Doctorate degree represent 31.25%. Furthermore, according to percent distribution of participation in the study from nursing departments it was indicated that nursing educators represent 26.25% from community health nursing, 17.5% from Medical surgical, 15% from Administration, 15% from pediatric, 13.75% from Psychiatric, and 12.5% from obstetric department. In addition, in the light of years of experience for the studied nursing educators the percent distribution was 37.75% for experience from 5 to 10 years, 33.75% for experience less than 5 years, and 28.75% for experience more than 10 years.

Table (2) illustrates the distribution of empowerment among the nursing educators. It was noticed that, majority of the study subjects reported moderate level in both psychological and structural empowerment dimensions. Related to psychological dimensions self-determination had the highest (83.75%) ranked of psychological empowerment dimensions followed by competence and meaning (82.5% and 80%) respectively. While, impact had the lowest (78.75%) ranked of psychological empowerment dimensions. Also, related to structural empowerment dimensions workplace culture had the highest (83.75%) ranked of structural empowerment dimensions followed by access to resources, access to strategic information (82.5%, 81.25%) respectively. While, sociopolitical support had the lowest (80%) ranked of structural empowerment dimension.

Table (3) present distribution of job commitment among the nursing educators. It was observed that the majority of the study subjects reported high job commitment dimensions. Also, it can be observed that continuance commitment had the highest percentage (87.5%) ranked of job commitment dimensions followed by Normative commitment (85%). The same table showed a statistically significant difference among all job commitment dimensions ($\chi^2 = 11.334, 30.040, 48.403$) respectively.

Table (4) shows the relationship between general characteristic of nursing educators and their psychological empowerment. It was observed that, statistically significant difference was found between psychological empowerment dimensions and both age and working nursing department at $p \leq 0.05$.

Table (5) shows the relationship between general characteristics of the nursing educators and their structural empowerment by using ANOVA test. It was noted that, statistically significant difference was found between structural empowerment dimensions and general characteristics of

the nursing educators (age, nursing educators' qualification, working department, and years of experience) at $p \leq 0.05$.

Table (6) illustrates the relationship between general characteristic of the nursing educators and their job commitment. It was demonstrated that, statistically significant difference was found between job commitment dimensions and general characteristics of the nursing educators (age, nursing educators' qualification, working department, and years of experience) at $p \leq 0.05$.

Table (7) illustrates correlation between empowerment and job commitment dimensions of the nursing educators. It was noticed that there were a highly statistically significant weak to fair positive correlation between all items of empowerment; continuous dimensions, most of normative and affective and job commitment dimensions of the nursing educators.

Discussion

Empowerment has been described as both a process and an outcome. Also, it was defined as "the interpersonal process of providing the resource, tools, and environment to develop, build, and increase ability and effectiveness of others to set and reach goals for individual and social ends. This definition aligns with the theory of structural empowerment, which relates to provision of resources, support and opportunities for learning to accomplish personal and professional goals. As an outcome, empowerment has been defined as possessing elements of self-efficacy, competency, autonomy and having meaning in ones' existence. Furthermore, Professional empowerment is a dynamic process, which occurs through interaction at the personal, professional, cultural and organizational levels. The existence of competent nurse educator who have a wide range of professional knowledge and skills, authority and self-confidence are considered essential for empowerment⁽¹⁹⁾.

The findings of present study revealed that the studied nursing educators have moderate level of all dimensions of empowerment (psychological and structural). In addition, self-determination was ranked as the highest psychological empowerment dimension and workplace culture as the highest structural empowerment dimension. This result was in agreement with Putranta (2011) who found that nurse educators had moderate levels of empowerment⁽²⁰⁾. Also, this finding explained by Livsey (2009) who stated that in the culture of the nurse educators examined, there was a self-determination to develop educational programs, policies and procedures, and other material even if they did not receive as much support in developing the product as they would have wanted⁽²¹⁾. On the other hand, this finding contradicted by Devin et al. (2013) they found that the mean scores of their study subjects empowerment perception were low⁽²²⁾. Moreover, these findings was also in contrast with Hosseini (2013) who found that lowest mean and standard deviation is respectively related to self-determination and competence⁽²³⁾.

Furthermore, this result might be attributed to the negative perceptions regarding workplace as slow salary and the unattractive work environments. Also, desire to leave Egypt, especially to the Gulf area, looking for better salary this is considered an alarming situation for Egyptian nursing educators workforce, which is suffering from shortage of the teaching staff as the shortage is likely to put extra burden on remaining teaching staff and increase their work-related stress. Where nursing educator's workforce in El-Minia faculty of nursing were 113 and total number of nursing students were 1105 for academic year 2013/2014.

Furthermore, the results of the present study demonstrated that the majority of the studied educators had high levels of all job commitment dimensions. The highest percent was found with continuance

commitment, followed by affective commitment, then, normative commitment. This result agree with Abood et al. (2011) they found a high level of organizational commitment among the studied nurses.⁽²⁴⁾ Moreover, this finding in the same line with Alam et al. (2013) they mentioned that the teachers of physical education had high job commitments⁽²⁵⁾. Additionally, El-Din and Abd-El-Rahman (2013) found that the commitment level was neither high nor low and this also is not surprising, this might be attributed to the humanistic nature of the nursing profession, whereby nurses feel they are committed to their mission regardless the compensation for achieving their duties and their satisfaction with this compensation⁽¹⁴⁾. On the other hand, this finding contradicted by Dorgham (2012) who found that the studied subjects had low commitment toward their organization, as they did not feel emotionally attached to their organization, or their organization did not deserved their loyalty⁽²⁶⁾.

In addition, this finding might be due to lack of alternative job opportunities such as other national or international universities so they are afraid to lose their jobs. Another explanation for this results may related to other factors such as a personal characteristic and individual's sense of duty to stay with a particular organization and/or an awareness of the costs associated with leaving the organization. Moreover, academics staff are probably less limited in their capacity to move between educational institutes and other sources of employment so this might responsible for the commitment.

Furthermore, results of the present study showed that a statistical significant relationship was found between studied nursing educators demographic characteristics (age, department, qualification, and years of experience) and structural empowerment dimension. These findings supported by Nikkhah (2010) who argued that empowerment can be measured directly through education level and

knowledge. Also, education has the strength to enable nursing educators to think critically and to question their disempowerment. Therefore, education could provide opportunities for nursing educators to evaluate themselves, and gradually develop self-confidence and a positive self-image so that they begin to appreciate their own capacities and potentialities⁽²⁷⁾.

Moreover, in the presents study a statistical significant relationship was found between general characteristics studied (age, working department, nursing educators qualification, and years of experience) and their job commitment. This finding goes in congruence with Dorgham (2012) who founded that demographic factors of workers significantly correlated with organizational commitment.⁽²⁶⁾ He added that older, married, more experienced and more educated workers had higher levels of organizational commitment than the younger, single, less experienced and less educated workers. On the other hand, this finding contradict with Cherabin et al. (2012) who reported that length of teaching experience and age of teachers did not have significant influence over their organizational commitment⁽⁸⁾.

Additionally, this could be due to when age increase, the employee's opportunities for alternative employment decrease, this limitation of the individual's options may increase the perceived attractiveness and attachments of the current organization. Because the longer the worker stay with an organization or the older they are the more time they have to evaluate their relationship with the organization. Also, employee who have been with their employing organizations for a long time are more likely to have embedded relationships and strong organization ties and the more social ties the employee develops in the organization, the more the individual becomes attached to the organization. Moreover, years of experience are also associated with firm- specific socialization

which ties the employee to a single organization and infuses core values in the employee

Also, this study proved the positive relationship between empowerment and job commitment among the studied nursing educators. It revealed a highly statistical significant positive weak correlation between most of empowerment dimensions and job commitment dimensions of the studied educators. This finding was consistent with Ahmad et al. (2014) they stated that it is important for organizations to put in place management systems and policies that foster an environment where employees feel empowered. An empowered work force will eventually get committed. Moreover, they indicated that teachers that believed in their own competence, ability to effect change, and impact students, actually they act according to their believes. Consequently, they also engage in more organization citizenship behavior, are more committed to and satisfied with their jobs and the schools they work for⁽⁵⁾.

This finding also explained by Cherabin et al. (2012) they stated that training opportunities, assignment to new roles and provision of flexible working conditions are associated with job commitment and more specifically, these practices are strongly associated with the willingness to remain in the organization⁽⁸⁾. Additionally, employees who accurately receive information from their supervisors about their work environment, are better informed, feel an integral part of the organization, therefore the higher their commitment to the organization^(28,29).

Moreover, climates that reflect flexible working conditions may help nursing educators to become more sensitive and willing to assist one another. This cooperation facilitates cohesion among academic staff members, which in turn lead to higher involvement in, and, commitment to the organization. Moreover, psychological empowerment is associated with job commitment because a person who

is able to understand and is aware of one's own feelings, and controls stress, negative emotions, and feelings of frustration, can certainly have better relationships with colleagues and supervisors, which ends in increasing job satisfaction, job commitment and better job performance.

Conclusion

- The studied nursing educators had moderate sense of empowerment and high level of job commitment.
- Positive weak to fair correlation was found between most of empowerment and job commitment dimensions of the studied nursing educators.
- There were relationship between age, education, working department, and experience of nursing educators with both empowerment and job commitment dimensions.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings of this study, the followings are recommendations:

A. Recommendations to enhance nursing educators' empowerment:

- Encourage nursing educators to attend national and international congress to enhance their empowerment.
- Nursing educators' should have continuous in-service training programs to maintain high academic standards in the teaching learning process and research.
- Provide educational opportunities for nursing educators to help them to evaluate themselves and develop self-confidence and positive self-image through enhancing their professional knowledge and skills.

B. Recommendations to maintain nursing educators' job commitment:

- Maintain positive emotional state and secure feeling of nursing educators through appreciation and reward.
- Developing trust, fairness, and better communication to nursing educators through good team working, respect for the roles and contributions of others.
- Provide necessary facilities, support, and take actions that cater for the welfare of the nursing educators such as improve salary and increase staff number to decrease work recalled stress.

C. Recommendations for future studies:

- Replication of the study with a larger sample to further validate the results.
- Conduct a study to explore the difference between job satisfaction, empowerment, and job commitment of nursing educators in Upper and North Egypt.

Table (1): Distribution of the nursing educators according to their general characteristics N = 80

General Characteristic	No	%
Age:		
21 ≤ 30	41	51.25
31 ≤ 40	28	35
40 <	11	13.75
Gender :		
▪ Male	6	7.5
▪ Female	74	92.5
Academic qualification:		
Baccalaureate degree	25	31.25
Master degree	30	37.5
Doctorate degree	25	31.25
Nursing department:		
• Medical surgical	14	17.5
• Pediatric	12	15
• Psychiatric	11	13.75
• Administration	12	15
• Obstetric	10	12.5
• Community health	21	26.25
Years of experience:		
Less than 5 years	27	33.75
From 5-10 years	30	37.5
More than 10 years	23	28.75

Table (2): Distribution of empowerment by the nursing educators N = 80

Empowerment Dimensions	Empowerment levels						χ^2	P-value
	Low (>46)		Moderate (46-90)		High (91-135)			
	No	%	No	%	No	%		
Psychological dimensions								
-Meaning	0	0.0	64	80	16	20	12.179	0.058
-Competence	0	0.0	66	82.5	14	17.5	47.677	0.0001**
-Self-Determination	0	0.0	67	83.75	13	16.25	31.854	0.0001**
- Impact	0	0.0	63	78.75	17	21.25	16.887	0.051*
Structural dimensions								
-Sociopolitical Support	0	0.0	64	80	16	20	49.312	0.0001**
-Access to Strategic Information	0	0.0	65	81.25	15	18.75	49.986	0.0001**
-Access to Resources	0	0.0	66	82.5	14	17.5	71.688	0.0001**
-Workplace culture	0	0.0	67	83.75	13	16.25	47.883	0.0001**

* Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.** Highly significant $p \leq 0.001$.

Table (3): Distribution of job commitment by the nursing educators N= 80

Job commitment dimensions	Job commitment Scores						χ^2	P-value
	Low (>46)		Moderate (46-90)		High (91-135)			
	No	%	No	%	No	%		
Affective	0	0.0	12	15	68	85	11.334	0.005**
Continuance	0	0.0	10	12.5	70	87.5	30.040	0.002**
Normative	0	0.0	14	17.5	66	82.5	48.403	0.0001**

* Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.** Highly significant $p \leq 0.001$.**Table (4): The relationship between General Characteristic of the nursing educators and their Psychological Empowerment**

General Characteristic	Psychological Empowerment dimensions			
	Meaning	Competence	Self-determination	Impact
	Mean+S.D	Mean+S.D	Mean+S.D	Mean+S.D
Age / years				
21 ≤ 30	12.5 ± 1.9	12.2 ± 2.0	11.6 ± 2.0	10.4 ± 2.2
31 ≤ 40	13.2 ± 1.6	12.7 ± 1.8	11.0 ± 1.9	9.9 ± 2.8
40 <	13.6 ± 1.5	14.4 ± 0.7	13.8 ± 1.3	13.1 ± 1.0
P- value	.665	.01*	.151	.110
Gender				
Male	12.0 ± 0.0	12.3 ± .5	12.0 ± 0.0	12.0 ± 0.0
Female	12.9 ± 1.8	12.7 ± 2.0	11.7 ± 2.2	10.5 ± 2.6
P- value	.197	.680	.708	.151
Academic qualification				
Baccalaureate	12.2 ± 1.8	12.1 ± 1.5	10.7 ± 2.1	9.6 ± 1.5
Master	13.2 ± 1.5	13.0 ± 1.8	12.3 ± 1.8	11.1 ± 2.1
Doctorate	13.1 ± 1.9	12.5 ± 2.6	11.6 ± 2.2	10.3 ± 3.7
P- value	.143	.245	.154	.386
Nursing department				
Medical surgical	13.2 ± 1.1	13.4 ± 1.1	11.6 ± 2.0	9.9 ± 3.5
Pediatric	13.5 ± 1.3	13.5 ± 1.7	13.0 ± 1.6	11.7 ± 2.6
Psychiatric	11.8 ± 1.9	13.1 ± 1.3	11.5 ± 1.4	10.4 ± 1.5
Administration	13.0 ± 1.5	11.8 ± 2.1	11.7 ± 3.1	10.3 ± 2.6
Obstetric	13.0 ± 2.4	12.4 ± 2.9	12.2 ± 1.9	11.4 ± 2.4
Community health	12.8 ± 1.9	12.0 ± 1.8	10.9 ± 1.9	10.3 ± 2.1
P- value	.007**	.001**	.002**	.001**
Years of experience				
Less than 5 years	12.7 ± 1.6	11.9 ± 1.5	11.6 ± 2	10.5 ± 1.9
From 5-10 years	12.8 ± 1.8	12.7 ± 2.6	11.3 ± 2.2	10.6 ± 2.6
More than 10 years	13.1 ± 1.8	13.5 ± 1.1	12.2 ± 2.2	10.7 ± 3.3
P- value	.419	.157	.351	.822

* Significant at $P \leq 0.01$ ** Highly Significant at $P \leq 0.001$

Table (5): The relationship between General Characteristic of the nursing educators and their Structural Empowerment

General Characteristic	Structural Empowerment dimensions			
	Sociopolitical support	Access to strategic information	Access to resources	Workplace culture
	Mean \pm S.D	Mean \pm S.D	Mean \pm S.D	Mean \pm S.D
Age/ years				
21 \leq 30	15.0 \pm 2.2	10.6 \pm 3.0	9.4 \pm 2.4	17.3 \pm 3.1
31 \leq 40	13.5 \pm 3.0	10.1 \pm 2.6	8.8 \pm 3.0	15.0 \pm 3.1
40 <	17.5 \pm 1.2	13.5 \pm 1.3	12.2 \pm 1.7	20.5 \pm 5.0
P- value	.0001**	.003**	.001**	.001**
Gender				
Male	13.7 \pm 2.3	11.0 \pm 1.5	9.7 \pm 1.9	17.7 \pm 2.3
Female	14.9 \pm 2.8	10.8 \pm 2.9	9.5 \pm 2.8	16.9 \pm 3.9
P- value	.102	.416	.483	.498
Academic qualification				
Baccalaureate	14.0 \pm 1.9	9.0 \pm 2.9	9.1 \pm 2.4	16.2 \pm 2.5
Master	15.2 \pm 3.2	11.5 \pm 2.3	9.2 \pm 3.1	17.8 \pm 3.2
Doctorate	14.8 \pm 2.8	11.3 \pm 2.8	10.1 \pm 2.6	16.0 \pm 4.3
P- value	.110	.001**	.196	.093
Nursing department				
Medical surgical	15.4 \pm 2.6	12.7 \pm 1.9	10.5 \pm 2.4	17.6 \pm 3.4
Pediatric	15.0 \pm 3.1	10.8 \pm 2.5	10.4 \pm 1.3	17.2 \pm 2.4
Psychiatric	15.4 \pm .8	10.6 \pm 2.0	10.3 \pm 2.1	15.6 \pm 3.1
Administration	13.5 \pm 3.5	10.4 \pm 3.6	9.2 \pm 4.2	18.8 \pm 5.9
Obstetric	16.2 \pm 1.2	11.8 \pm 1.7	9.4 \pm 2.5	17.0 \pm 3.7
Community health	14.2 \pm 3.1	9.4 \pm 3.4	8.2 \pm 2.6	16.1 \pm 3.3
P- value	.0001**	.005**	.0001**	.0001**
Years of experience				
Less than 5 years	14.5 \pm 2.1	10.1 \pm 3.2	9 \pm 2.5	17.5 \pm 3.4
From 5-10 years	14.6 \pm 3.9	10.5 \pm 2.9	9 \pm 3.2	15.7 \pm 3.3
More than 10 years	15.5 \pm 1.7	12.1 \pm 2.2	10.7 \pm 1.9	18.1 \pm 4.5
P- value	.96	.003**	.065	.001**

* Significant at $P \leq 0.05$ ** Highly Significant at $P \leq 0.001$

Table (6): The relationship between General Characteristic of the nursing educators and their job commitment

General Characteristic	Job commitment		
	Affective	Continuance	Normative
	Mean \pm S.D	Mean \pm S.D	Mean \pm S.D
Age/ years			
21 \leq 30	19.2 \pm 3.7	20.1 \pm 2.9	15.3 \pm 4.7
31- \leq 40	19.1 \pm 2.7	21.7 \pm 2.4	17.6 \pm 2.9
40 <	21.4 \pm 5.9	23.6 \pm 2.6	16.8 \pm 5.9
P- value	.002**	.001**	.001**
Gender			
Male	20.0 \pm 3.1	20.7 \pm 2.1	14.7 \pm 3.7
Female	19.4 \pm 3.9	21.2 \pm 2.9	16.5 \pm 4.5
P- value	.721	.675	.344
Academic qualification			
Baccalaureate	18.6 \pm 2.6	19.4 \pm 2.5	18.4 \pm 4.5
Master	19.1 \pm 4.0	21.4 \pm 2.5	15.4 \pm 5.0
Doctorate	19.9 \pm 2.6	22.1 \pm 2.7	16.2 \pm 2.3
P- value	.114	.001**	.002**
Nursing department			
Medical surgical	19.1 \pm 2.2	22.7 \pm 1.4	19.6 \pm 4.4
Pediatric	18.8 \pm 2.9	20.8 \pm 2.1	15.5 \pm 4.1
Psychiatric	19.7 \pm 2.8	19.7 \pm 2.1	17.5 \pm 2.3
Administration	20.4 \pm 6.5	21.3 \pm 3.7	14.4 \pm 3.0
Obstetric	20.2 \pm 5.5	23.2 \pm 1.5	12.2 \pm 4.9
Community health	19.0 \pm 2.6	19.9 \pm 3.6	17.0 \pm 4.2
P- value	.453	.001**	.001**
Years of experience			
Less than 5 years	19.3 \pm 4.1	20.1 \pm 2.7	15.4 \pm 5.1
From 5-10 years	19.6 \pm 2.7	21.1 \pm 3.1	16.9 \pm 4.1
More than 10 years	19.5 \pm 4.8	22.6 \pm 2.4	17.0 \pm 4.1
P-value	.859	.001**	.235

* Significant at $P \leq 0.05$ ** Highly Significant at $P \leq 0.001$

Table (7): Pearson Correlation between empowerment and job commitment of nursing educators N=80

Empowerment Dimensions	Job commitment Dimensions					
	Affective		Continuance		Normative	
	r	P-value	r	P-value	r	P-value
Meaning	0.195	0.083	0.490**	0.0001	0.288*	0.01
Competence	0.105	0.355	0.124	0.274	0.133	0.240
Self-Determination	0.207	0.066	0.303**	0.006	0.220*	0.050
Impact	0.327**	0.003	0.193	0.086	0.377**	0.001
Sociopolitical Support	0.140	0.215	0.247*	0.027	0.146	0.196
Access to Strategic Information	0.320**	0.004	0.601**	0.0001	0.332**	0.003
Access to Resources	0.194	0.085	0.225*	0.045	0.030	0.790
Workplace culture	0.103	0.363	0.347**	0.002	0.223*	0.047

* Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.** Highly significant $p \leq 0.001$.

Spearman Rho correlation coefficient

r = 0.00 to 0.24 weak or no correlation

r = 0.25 to 0.49 Fair correlation

r = 0.50 to 0.74 moderate correlation

r = 0.75 + strong correlation

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